

Batteries & Supercaps

Supporting Information

Hybrid based on Phenazine Conjugated Microporous Polymer as a High-Performance Organic Electrode in Aqueous Electrolytes

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Experimental Section

Synthesis of 2,7-dibromophenazine (2):

Step 1

Step 2

Scheme S1. Synthesis of 2,7-dibromophenazine (**2**).

Synthesis of IEP-27-SR by miniemulsion polymerization and solvothermal approach:

STEP 1: Miniemulsion polymerization

STEP 2: Solvothermal treatment

Scheme S2. Synthesis of IEP-27-SR. Inclusion of carbon additives have been excluded in the schematic for the sake of clarity.

Figure S1. ^1H NMR spectrum of 2,7-dibromophenazine (**2**). The numerical allocated in the chemical structure is correspond to its NMR peak assignment.

Figure S2. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 2,7-dibromophenazine (**2**). The numerical allocated in the chemical structure is correspond to its NMR peak assignment.

Table S1. Textural parameters of IEP-27-SR obtained from N_2 adsorption–desorption isotherms at 77 K.

Polymer	$S_{\text{BET}}^{\text{a}}$	$S_{\text{micro/DFT}}^{\text{b}}$ $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$	$S_{\text{meso/DFT}}^{\text{b}}$ $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$	$S_{\text{micro/DFT}}$ (%)	$S_{\text{meso/DFT}}$ (%)	$V_{\text{tot}}^{\text{c}}$ $\text{m}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$
IEP-27-SR	765	349	416	46	54	0.92

^aSpecific surface area calculated using Brunauer-Emmett-Teller method. ^bmicroporous and mesoporous surface area determined using QSDFT method. ^cTotal pore volume calculated from QSDFT model.

Figure S3. Pore-size distribution of IEP-27-SR from the quenched solid density functional theory (QSDFT) model.

Figure S4. (a) XRD spectrum, (b) EDS spectra, SEM image merge with elements mapping and elements mapping (C, N) and (c, d) TEM pictures of IEP-27-SR. Scale bar in c and d is 200 nm, and 1 μ m, respectively.

Figure S5. CVs of IEP-27-SR in aqueous (buffer)solutions, pH = 0–14, evaluated in the three-electrode configuration. (a) strong acid-to-mild acidic conditions, pH = 0 – 4, (b) mild acidic-to-mild basic conditions, including neutral regime, pH = 5.5 – 10, and (c) mild basic-to-strong basic conditions, pH = 12 – 14.

Figure S6. *ex-situ* FTIR spectra of the pristine, discharged (reduced) and recharged (reoxidised) IEP-27-SR buckypaper electrode in acidic (1 M H₂SO₄) medium.

Figure S7. Normalized specific capacity of the CVs at 5 mV s^{-1} in a series of Britton-Robinson universal buffer solutions, $1.1 < \text{pH} < 12$, including pH 14 (1 M KOH). The specific capacities at higher pH values were normalized by specific capacity at pH 1.1.

Figure S8. Scan rate-dependency of IEP-27-SR buckypaper electrodes by CV in Britton-Robinson universal buffer solutions at pH 1.1 and 4 to evaluate mass-transfer limited behavior. (a, b) CVs at different scan rates at pH 1.1 (a), and pH 4 (b), the corresponding specific capacities (c), and their retention (d). The specific capacities at higher scan rates were normalized by specific capacity at 0.25 mV s^{-1} .

Computational methods and results

Quantum-chemical calculations based on density functional (DFT) and wave function theory (WFT) are performed to get additional insights into the reduction of phenazine with protons and potassium cations. The structure of the polymer is truncated to a simple monomer redox core that is composed by a phenazine molecule. The protons are modelled as solvated H_3O^+ that is hydrogen-bonded with 3 H_2O molecules. Similarly, the potassium cations are considered to have their first coordination sphere solvated with 6 H_2O molecules. When required for balancing a reaction, the energy of a single H_2O molecules is taken as the energy difference between $(H_2O)_5$ and $(H_2O)_4$. The following reduction reactions are considered for protons and potassium cations:

The geometries of all species in the gas phase are optimized using DFT. The r^2 SCAN-3c functional in combination with the def2-mTZVPP basis set is used to optimize the geometries in the gas phase.^[18] A subsequent frequency calculation is performed and all structures are confirmed to be minima with no imaginary frequencies. The thermal corrections (G_{therm}) to the free energies are calculated assuming $T = 298.15$ K and $P = 1$ atm, based on the quantum mechanical harmonic-oscillator approximation from the vibrational partition functions. Frequencies with values lower than 50 cm^{-1} , are shifted to values of 50 cm^{-1} , in the calculation of the entropic and enthalpic terms, as implemented in the Shermo code.^[19] The effect of the solvent (ΔG^{solv}) is estimated by the difference between a gas and solution phase calculation using the M06-2X functional in combination with the def2-TZVPP basis set at the optimized geometries.^[20] The solvent is treated by the implicit solvation model SMD,^[21] thus $\Delta G^{\text{solv}} = E^{\text{gas}}[\text{M06-2X/def2-TZVPP}] - E^{\text{SMD}}[\text{M06-2X/def2-TZVPP}]$. In all DFT calculations, very accurate settings are chosen: “VeryTightSCF” for the SCF convergence, “TightOpt” for the geometry optimization and “DEFGRID3” for the grid settings. Finally, the electronic energies are taken from the accurate DLPNO-CCSD(T1) method with the def2-QZVPP basis set.^[22] The DLPNO-CCSD(T1) calculations will allow us to get the best estimate of the electronic energies. The final solution free energies ($G^{0, \text{sol}}$) for each species are taken as: $G^{0, \text{sol}} = E_{\text{gas}}[\text{DLPNO-CCSD(T1)/def2-QZVPP}] + G_{\text{therm}}^{\text{gas}}[\text{r}^2\text{SCAN-3c/def2-mTZVPP}] + \Delta G^{\text{solv}}[\text{M06-2X/def2-TZVPP}]$. The effect of the different concentrations of protons and

potassium cations is also considered by adding the term $RT\ln\frac{Q^{0'}}{Q^0}$ to the reduction free energies, where $Q^{0'}$ is the desired concentration, while the standard-state concentrations Q^0 are assumed to be 1 M. All calculations have been performed with the ORCA 5.0.3 code.^[23]

The systems studied are shown in Figure S9.

Figure S9. Models used in the computational study: A) oxonium cation (H_3O^+) solvated with 3 water molecules, B) water tetramer, C) water pentamer, D) potassium cation solvated with 6 water molecules, E) phenazine in the oxidized form, F) phenazine reduced with 2 protons, G) phenazine reduced with 2 potassium cations (each potassium is solvated with 6 water molecules), and H) phenazine reduced with 2 potassium cations (each potassium is solvated with 5 water molecules).

The computed free energies of reduction are shown in Table S3. For potassium, the reduction energies have been calculated by considering two different stoichiometric reactions, by considering $z=0$ and $z=1$ in the equation S2. At these basic conditions, the following pH values are taken depending on the concentration of KOH: 14 for 1M KOH, 15 for 4M KOH and 15.5 for 10M KOH. In the first three cases (pH of 1, 4, 7), the reduction with 2 potassium cations is also computed by considering the presence of 4M KCl.

Table S3. Computed free energies of reaction (in kcal/mol) in different pH, [KOH] and [KCl] conditions.

	pH=1 (4M KCl)	pH=4 (4M KCl)	pH=7 (4M KCl)	pH=14 (1M KOH)	pH=15 (4M KOH)	pH=15.5 (10M KOH)
$\text{PZ} + 2(\text{H}_3\text{O})^+(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3 + 2\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{PZ-H}_2 + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$	-206.9	-196.0	-187.8	-168.7	-166.0	-164.7
$\text{PZ} + 2\text{K}^+(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6 + 2\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{PZ-2}[\text{K}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$	-162.8	-162.8	-162.8	-161.1	-162.8	-163.9
$\text{PZ} + 2\text{K}^+(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6 + 2\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{PZ-2}[\text{K}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5] + 2(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	-155.7	-155.7	-155.7	-154.1	-155.7	-156.8

Figure S10. 3 electrode study in different neutral electrolytes using modified glassy carbon as WE: (a) CV at 5 mVs^{-1} in 5M KCl, 5M LiCl, 5M NaCl; (b) CV at 5 mVs^{-1} in different NaCl concentrations.

Figure S11. Electrochemical performance of IEP-27-SR in 1 and 10 M LiTFSI at C/5 and C/2, evaluated using two electrodes cell against oversized AC.

Figure S12. Correlation between the redox peak position and the formal potential on logarithm of [Na⁺]. The peak potential values are taken from CV studies in 3 electrodes at different NaCl concentrations, represented in Figure S10b.

Note: As the concentrations of Na^+ in the electrolyte increase, the formal potential ($E_{1/2}$) increase linearly with a positive slope. This is typically a Nernst-type behavior, where the $E_{1/2}$ demonstrated linear dependency on the activity of the Na^+ (a_{Na^+}):^{[1][2]}

$$E_{1/2} = E^0 + \frac{0.059}{n} \log a_{\text{Na}^+}$$

However, the obtained slope was $20 \text{ mV}/[\text{Na}^+]$, which is lower than ideal $59 \text{ mV}/[\text{Na}^+]$, if one-to-one stoichiometry between electrons and Na^+ is involved in the redox reactions. This lower value of slope once again suggests mixed H^+ and Na^+ charge storage in the neutral electrolyte.

Figure S13. CV of IEP-27-SR at 5 mV s^{-1} in 1M of each LiOH, NaOH, and KOH in 3 electrodes.

Figure S14. CV of IEP-27-SR at 5 mV s^{-1} in different KOH concentrations (1, 5, 10 M) in 3 electrodes.

Figure S15. The convergence of ΔG difference values for the reduction of phenazine with H^+ and K^+ charge carriers with the increase of pH, as computed by DFT calculations.

Figure S16. Specific capacities (a), and their retention (b), quantified from CV analyses of IEP-27-SR buckypaper electrodes in 1 M H₂SO₄ and 5 M KOH at various scan rates (Figure 5a, d in the main manuscript). The specific capacities at higher scan rates were normalized by specific capacity at 0.1 mV s⁻¹.

Figure S17. Cycling performance of AC//IEP-27-SR in the aqueous electrolyte 5M KOH; (a) long cycling at 2C; (b) representative galvanostatic capacity–potential profiles at 2C.

Figure S18. Representative galvanostatic capacity–potential profiles of AC//IEP-27-SR at 10C, (a) in the aqueous electrolyte 5M KOH and, (b) in the aqueous electrolyte 1M H₂SO₄.

Figure S19. (a) Long-term cycling performance of AC//IEP-27-SR at 2C in the aqueous electrolyte 1M H₂SO₄; (b) representative galvanostatic capacity–potential profiles at 2C.

Figure S20. Coulombic efficiency evaluation of AC//IEP-27-SR (a) at a fixed voltage window from -0.6 to 0.3 V (vs AC), but at various C-rates, and (b) at a fixed 2C rate, but with variable upper voltage limits from +0.2 to +0.5 V (vs AC).

Table S4. Comparison of electrochemical performance of IEP-27-SR specifically specific capacity/capacitance and cycle stability, in acidic electrolyte with various organic electrode materials reported in literature.

active-material	electrolyte	voltage window (vs reference electrode)	specific capacitance (F/g) or specific capacity (mAh/g) (at current density or C-rate)	cycle performance: % C_s , retention; number of cycles; speed (C-rate or current density)	Ref
Small molecules					
NTCDA	2 M MnSO ₄ +2 M H ₂ SO ₄	-0.3 to 0.5V (Ag/AgCl)	88 mAh/g 1 A/g	66% 3500 cycles 1 A/g	[3]
PTO	2 M MnSO ₄ +2 M H ₂ SO ₄	0.0 to 0.7V V (Ag/AgCl)	208 mAh/g 0.2 C	78% 1000 cycles 2.5 C	[4]
MB-45	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	0.0 to 0.9V (SHE)	317.7 F/g 0.5 A/g	90% 3000 cycles 5 A/g	[5]
PPy/MB	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	-0.2-0.6 V (Ag/AgCl)	12.7 mF/cm 50 μ A/cm	95.6% 2000 cycles 200 mV s ⁻¹	[6]
Linear polymers					
PEDOT/Au/PEN	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	0.3 to -0.5 V (Ag/AgCl)	300 F cm ⁻³ 1 mA/cm ²	87% 10 000 cycle 2 mA/cm ²	[7]
PANI-CP	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	-0.2 to 0.8 V (SCE)	207.41 mF/ cm ² 20 A/g	85% 1000 cycles 50 mA/cm ²	[8]
pDTP-AQ	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	-0.5 to 0.9 V (Ag/AgCl)	120 mAh/g 5C	83% 1000 cycles 10C	[9]
pEP(QH2)E	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	0.5 to 0.8V	75 mAh/g	87%	[10]

		(SHE)	3C	100 cycles 3C	
pEP(NQ)E	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	0 to 0.5V (SHE)	70 mAh/g 3C	90% 100 cycles 3C	[10]
PTC	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	-0.4 to 0.2 V (Ag/AgCl)	83.2 mAh/g 1 A/g	80% 1000 cycles 5 A/g	[11]
PUQ	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	-0.4 to 0.2 V (Ag/AgCl)	94.2 mAh/g 1 A/g	82% 1000 cycles 5 A/g	[11]
Porous polymers					
Hex-Aza-COF-3	PVA-1 M H ₂ SO ₄	0 to 1.7V (RuO ₂)	64 F/g 1 A/g	89% 7500 cycles 5 A/g	[12]
PEDOT modified- DAAQ–TFP COF	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	-0.7 to 0 (AC)	410 F cm ⁻³ 10C	no decay 10000 cycles 100C	[13]
3Qn-CMP/rGO	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	-0.4 to 0.8 V (Ag/AgCl)	847.8 F/g 1 A/g	99.1% 50000 cycles 50 A/g	[14]
1-OH COF	PVA-1 M H ₂ SO ₄	0 to 0.8V (SHE)	92 mF/cm ² 0.5 mA/cm ²	83% 10000 cycles 500 mA/g	[15]
2-OH COF	PVA-1 M H ₂ SO ₄	0 to 0.8V (SHE)	32 mF/cm ² 0.5 mA/cm ²	88% 10000 cycles 500 mA/g	[15]
3-OH COF	PVA-1 M H ₂ SO ₄	0 to 0.8V (SHE)	57 mF/cm ² 0.5 mA/cm ²	95% 10000 cycles 500 mA/g	[15]
2KT-Tp COF	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	0.0 to 0.6 V (Ag/AgCl)	256 F/g 0.2 A/g	94% 20000 5 A/g	[16]
4KT-Tp COF	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	0.0 to 0.6 V (Ag/AgCl)	583 F/g 0.2 A/g	92% 20000 5 A/g	[16]
1KT-Tp COF	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	0.0 to 0.6 V (Ag/AgCl)	61 F/g 0.2 A/g	96% 20000 5 A/g	[16]
H-CMP-BPPB	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	-0.5 to 0.5 (H- CMP-BPPB)	130 F/g 0.5 A/g	90% 10 000 cycles 1 A/g	[17]
IEP-27-SR	1 M H₂SO₄	-0.6 to 0.3 (AC)	168 mAh/g 2C	76% 28800 10C	This work

Supplementary References

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